

Climate change impacts on renewable groundwater resources in the andosol-dominated Andean highlands, Ecuador

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Abstract

Climate change, coupled with adaptive human actions, will affect water resource access and availability for environmental requirements. Hydrological modelling is an effective strategy for forecasting climate and human impacts on water resources. Modelling tools are advised for sparse-data mountainous basins intended to supply densely populated urban areas in the future. In this context, the SWAT model is used to evaluate the impact of climate change on renewable groundwater resources in the Pita River basin (PRB), a representative area of the andosol-dominated *páramo* ecosystem in the Andean highlands projected to meet future water demand in the metropolitan district of Quito (MDQ), Ecuador. Based on data availability, a SWAT model is configured for the PRB over the period 2006–2015 and five regional climate models (RCMs) based on two Representative Concentration Pathway (RCP) emission scenarios (4.5 and 8.5) for the mid- (2040–2069) and long-term (2070–2099) future horizons are implemented. Hydrological modelling demonstrates increases in average temperature and precipitation of +2°C and +3% in the mid-term and +4.5°C and +20% in the long term, respectively. All the RCMs indicate less aquifer recharge in the mid-term. However, this pattern is softened, and even reversed, in several scenarios in the long term. Seasonal differences in streamflow and aquifer recharge in the baseline scenario are predicted to increase to +23%. The natural hydrological regime determined by thick porous allophane-rich andosols over virtually full moderate-permeability volcanic and volcano-sedimentary aquifers induces high streamflow and low aquifer recharge rates. Future hydrological regime could place the highly sensitive soil–vegetation dynamics of the *páramo* ecosystem at risk of degradation, with negative consequences for habitat preservation, in general, and stream water provision, in particular. Hence, groundwater is the safest option for water provision in the future.

Keywords: Climate change, Andean highlands, *páramo* ecosystem, andosols, SWAT model, Ecuador

1. Introduction

Climate change, coupled with particular adaptive human actions, will introduce a variety of physical and biological effects that directly impact hydrological processes and indirectly affect water availability for human and environmental requirements (Bovolo et al., 2009; Green et al., 2011, 2007). In mountainous regions, climate change is expected to strongly modify

51 temporal and spatial temperature and precipitation patterns, with significant consequences for
52 freshwater provision in low-lying areas (Kilsby et al., 2007; López-Moreno et al., 2011).
53 According to projected regional climate scenarios, changes in long-term precipitation and
54 temperature regimes are likely to increase the frequency and intensity of extreme rainfall events
55 and dry spells, altering the dynamics of crucial water balance components such as soil moisture,
56 streamflow and infiltration (Blanco-Gómez et al., 2019; Buytaert et al., 2010; Green et al., 2011;
57 Mishra et al., 2018; Pulido-Velazquez et al., 2018) with repercussions for water supply, food
58 provision, hydropower generation and the preservation of dependent ecosystems. In
59 mountainous areas, identifying water resource generation mechanisms and quantifying the
60 extent of renewable groundwater within the water balance are the first steps towards sustainable
61 water policies under a global warming framework.

62 In temperate mid-terrestrial latitudes, mountain regions play a crucial role in regional
63 freshwater supply and are highly sensitive to climate change (Barnett et al., 2005; Bradley et
64 al., 2006; Rangwala and Miller, 2012; Viviroli et al., 2011). High mountain basins, including
65 those partially headed by temperate glacier patches with a base at melting point (Cuffey and
66 Paterson, 2010; Van Vliet-Lanoë, 2014), have been preferentially studied for surface hydrology
67 purposes and soil-vegetation eco-systemic surveys. However, the renewable groundwater
68 component determined by the fraction of precipitation that infiltrates below the soil-root zone
69 and reaches the underground water table (hereafter called aquifer recharge) has rarely been
70 considered, even though evolving groundwater dynamics (recharge, discharge and storage)
71 must be assessed to forecast the evolution of freshwater resources under changing climatic
72 forces and adaptive human actions (Vincent et al., 2019).

73 The northern Andean highlands roughly extend between the latitudes 11°N and 8°S,
74 from Costa Rica to northern Peru, and lie over 3,000 m above sea level (m a.s.l). This region
75 lies in the Inter-Andean Valley (IAV), the western flank of the Eastern Andean Cordillera (EAC)
76 and the eastern flank of the Western Andean Cordillera (WAC). The *páramo* ecosystem
77 dominates the landscape. This neotropical alpine grassland ecosystem consists of steep, mostly
78 glacier-formed valleys and plains with a large variety of lakes, peat bogs and wet grasslands
79 intermingled with shrublands and low-bearing forest patches (Buytaert et al., 2006). This
80 tropical alpine environment hosts unique flora and fauna, and biodiversity plays an essential
81 role for local communities (Myers et al., 2000). The ensemble formed by thick porous
82 allophane-rich andosols over moderate-permeability volcanic and volcano-sedimentary
83 formations and crystalline rocks determines the hydrological functioning of the *páramo*
84 ecosystem (Clapperton, 1993; Garrison et al., 2011; Rose, 1996; Spikings et al., 2000). As in
85 other high mountain areas, most ecosystem typologies in the Andean highlands are groundwater
86 dependent (Bradley et al., 2006; Buytaert et al., 2006; Ochoa-Tocachi et al., 2018, 2016; Urrutia
87 and Vuille, 2009; Zulkafli et al., 2016) and streamflow is the accessible water source for local
88 communities and densely populated low-lying areas, for hydropower generation and irrigation,
89 because of the difficulty in accessing groundwater (Buytaert et al., 2005b, 2006; Vergara et al.,
90 2007). Hydrological literature on the Andean highlands, as in other mountainous regions,
91 primarily refers to surface hydrology processes preferentially studied in small catchments over
92 short monitoring periods (Buytaert et al., 2006, 2005a, 2004; Célleri and Feyen, 2009; Tovar et
93 al., 2013). Applied studies concerning the renewable groundwater component (recharge,
94 discharge and storage) or more advanced studies focused on the impact of climate change on
95 this resource in large basins are insignificant in number or virtually non-existent (Baraer et al.,
96 2014; Favier et al., 2008; Hemmings et al., 2016; Ruiz-Pico et al., 2019; Vuille et al., 2018).
97 The scant knowledge about groundwater systems in the Andean highlands derives from limited
98 groundwater accessibility, few operational weather and stream-gauging stations, a lack of
99 detailed geological and soil maps and sparse hydraulic and soil-vegetation data. In recent
100 decades, climate records for the Andean highlands have also revealed perturbing changes in

101 precipitation and temperature regimes (Espinoza-Villar et al., 2009), the consequences of which
102 for soil moisture, streamflow and renewable groundwater remain largely unknown.

103 The Pita River basin (PRB) is a representative area of the *páramo* ecosystem in the
104 northern Andean highlands in Ecuador with relatively high data density and null groundwater
105 abstraction and where the natural state of soils, streams and aquifers is well preserved. This
106 pristine andosol-dominated basin was selected to evaluate the impact of climate change on
107 renewable groundwater resources due to its representativeness, minimum data coverage
108 requirement and potential to supply approximately 400,000 inhabitants in the MDQ in the near
109 future. Hence, this basin is significant for future water resource assessment and management
110 by local water authorities. This situation is similar to that reported in other large urban areas in
111 the Andean highlands due to the expected reduction in renewable water resources and the
112 increasing population's water use habits.

113 This paper evaluates the impact of climate change on renewable groundwater resources
114 in the PRB. The results intend to illustrate how climate change could modify the regime of this
115 barely known resource, which is destined to meet most future water demand. The
116 methodological route to achieving this aim includes two stages. First, the semi-distributed
117 rainfall–runoff SWAT model (Arnold et al., 1998) is implemented, calibrated and validated over
118 the period 2006–2015. Next, the variables of a climate change prediction ensemble consisting
119 of five RCMs (ESM2M, HadGEM2-ES, IPSL-CM5A-LR, MIROC and NoerESM1-M) using
120 the RPC 4.5 and 8.5 emission scenarios for the mid- (2040–2069) and long-term (2070–2099)
121 future horizons are implemented into the SWAT model to generate future streamflow series,
122 from which the impacts of climate change on the renewable groundwater resources are assessed.
123 This paper is organised as follows: Section 2 describes the characteristics of the selected study
124 area, situated in Ecuador, which serves as a representative area of the *páramo* ecosystem in the
125 Andean highlands. Section 3 introduces the methodology, and Section 4 analyses and discusses
126 the SWAT model results, projected variations in precipitation and temperature regimes and
127 renewable groundwater resource response to climate change in the mid and long-term future
128 horizons. Section 5 presents the main conclusions and recommendations.

129

130 **2. Study area**

131

132 The PRB is located 50 km southeast of Quito city (0°29'–0°41' S, 78°19'–78°26' W)
133 in northern Ecuador (Figure 1a), covers an area of 184.5 km² and has a mean elevation of 4,008
134 m a.s.l. The basin is bounded by the north-eastern flank of the Cotopaxi Volcano and the south-
135 western flank of the Sincholagua Volcano (Figure 1b) and lies in the IAV between the EAC and
136 WAC. The Pita River is a tributary of the Esmeraldas River in the Pacific Ocean watershed
137 (Figure 1a).

138 This area exhibits a neotropical high mountain climate determined by its steep
139 orography, the El Niño–Southern Oscillation oceanographic phenomena and the Humboldt
140 current (Bendix, 2000; Bendix et al., 2004; González-Zeas et al., 2019). The distribution of
141 biozones includes tropical mountain rainforests in low-lying areas, the *paramo* ecosystem in
142 mid-slope areas and highlands, dry and cold scrublands in summit areas and permanent snow
143 cover on volcano peaks (Buytaert et al., 2006). The *páramo* ecosystem dominates most of the
144 PRB landscape.

145

146
 147 **Figure 1.** (a) The northern Andean highlands dominated by the *páramo* ecosystem from Costa Rica to Peru after
 148 Buytaert et al. (2006), indicating the PRB's location in northern Ecuador and other sites cited in the text. (b) A 30-
 149 m-resolution DEM of the PRB (from the SavGIS website: <http://www.savgis.org/ecuador.htm>) displaying the
 150 location of weather stations and stream-gauging station A1 (as in Table 2) and four illustrative views. (c)
 151 Hydrogeological map (scale 1:50,000) of the PRB, after literature data (Clapperton, 1993; Hall and Mothes, 2008)
 152 and direct field observations, indicating the location of the permanent Chilcahuayco spring (S1) contributing to

153 baseflow and regional piezometry in the synthetic hydrogeological cross-section A–A'. (d) Soil map (scale
154 1:200,000) of the PRB after Mejía et al., (1978) and direct field observations, showing the location of soil samples
155 s1 to s4 (as in Table 1) after Lahuette and Recalde (2015). (e) Land-use units of the PRB (scale 1:25,000) after
156 FONAG (2022), aerial photographs and direct field observations, illustrating the surface covered by the Cotopaxi
157 National Park (CNP) and the High Pita Water Conservation Area (HPWCA). (f) Views of 1—Bocatoma gauging
158 station (A1) and andesitic lavas from the Cotopaxi Volcano sequence (COVS) at the PRB outlet; 2—typical
159 leptosol over ash flows from COVS; 3—baseflow spring S1 discharging into the Pita River; and 4—typical andosol
160 of the *páramo* ecosystem over pyroclastic flows from the Chalupas Volcano sequence (CHVS). IAV—Inter-
161 Andean Valley; EAC—Eastern Andean Cordillera; WAC—Western Andean Cordillera; PW—Pacific watershed;
162 AW—Atlantic watershed; ERV—Esmeraldas River watershed; SIVS—Sincholagua Volcano sequence (SIVS);
163 SW—volumetric soil-water content at saturation ($\text{cm}^3 \text{cm}^{-3}$); T—temperature; P—precipitation.
164

165 Most precipitation (P) occurs in February–May, whereas the lowest amount is recorded
166 in July–September (Rollenbeck et al., 2006). Annual mean P is around 1,100 mm with a
167 coefficient of variation of 0.21 over the period 1964–2017. Precipitation follows a decreasing
168 gradient from east to west controlled by the incoming Atlantic cloud fronts and elevation
169 (Garreaud and Falvey, 2008; Makowski Giannoni et al., 2016). Annual mean temperature (T)
170 is around 7.5 °C, with daily minimums in June–September and maximums in February–April;
171 the daily amplitude can be as high as 19 °C in highlands and around 10°C in low-lying areas.
172 Annual mean potential evapotranspiration is around 1,000 mm.

173 From a hydrogeological perspective (Figure 1c), the PRB lies in the IAV, where various
174 Quaternary volcanic and volcano-sedimentary formations from the Sincholagua, Cotopaxi and
175 Chalupas stratovolcanoes are unconformably deposited over a Palaeozoic metapelitic
176 basement, which does not outcrop in the area (Garrison et al., 2011; Spikings et al., 2000), with
177 the following synthetic succession from bottom to top (Hall and Mothes, 2008; Hall and Wood,
178 1985): (1) early to late Pleistocene andesitic lavas and rhyolitic pyroclastic flows from the
179 Sincholagua (SIVS), Cotopaxi (COVS) and Chalupas (CHVS) volcano sequences; and (2) late
180 Pleistocene to Holocene ash flows, extensive avalanche flows, lahars, andesitic lavas, pumice
181 flows and scoria flows from COVS. The Quaternary sedimentary formations (Clapperton, 1993;
182 Rose, 1996) comprise (1) Pleistocene to Holocene fluvial-glacial deposits, (2) Holocene alluvial
183 deposits filling the Pita River valley, and (3) current glacier and moraines at the Cotopaxi
184 Volcano peak.

185 Two moderate-permeability aquifers, separated by aquitards, are located in the PRB.
186 The shallow aquifer is formed by Holocene andesitic lavas and avalanche flows from COVS
187 and late Pleistocene rhyolitic pyroclastic flows from CHVS. The deep aquifer is formed by
188 middle Pleistocene andesitic lavas from COVS and early Pleistocene andesitic lavas from SIVS
189 (Figure 1c). As in other Andean highlands, a noticeable permeability contrast exists between
190 thick porous soils (predominantly andosols) and volcanic and volcano-sedimentary formations,
191 determining high interflow runoff rates (Buytaert et al., 2005a, 2006; Célleri and Feyen, 2009;
192 Flores-López et al., 2016b). However, aquifer recharge to shallow and deep aquifers is possible
193 from (i) direct rainfall and interflow runoff infiltration (and de-icing to a slight extent) in
194 unconfined high-elevation areas (Hemmings et al., 2016; Vuille et al., 2018) and (ii) preferential
195 rainfall and runoff infiltration through shallow fissured geological formations when they are
196 hydraulically connected to the deep aquifer (Alcalá, 2016; Changkuon et al., 1989). Most
197 aquifer discharge occurs where the topography of the incisive valleys intersects the regional
198 piezometry to produce permanent baseflow springs that contribute significantly to streamflow
199 (Figure 1c).

200 Organic-carbon-rich andosols predominate in the cold and wet *páramo* ecosystem in the
201 PRB. Andosols are dark, humic and allophane-rich with a porous structure (Flores-López et al.,
202 2016b). These features, together with Al-rich clay mineral assemblages and organic-carbon
203 contents of between 10% and 40%, determine volumetric soil-water contents at saturation of
204 between $0.5 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ cm}^{-3}$ and $0.7 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ cm}^{-3}$, with exceptional values up to $0.9 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ cm}^{-3}$ (Figure

205 1d). This figures induce soil infiltration capacities in the 20–60 mm h⁻¹ range that can exceed
206 typical rainfall intensities in the study area (Buytaert et al., 2006, 2005a, 2005b; Célleri and
207 Feyen, 2009).

208 The PRB's soil typologies include 71.1% organic-carbon-rich andosols, 9.2% arenosols
209 on northern slopes, 8.2% leptosols over lahars and ash flows in the Pita River valley, 7.5%
210 regosols in summit areas, 3.3% phaeozems over fluvial-glacial sediments above 4,000 m a.s.l.,
211 and less than 1% is the Cotopaxi Volcano glacier (Figure 1d) (Mejía et al., 1978). Regarding
212 land use, 73.4% of the PRB is covered by xerophytic tussock grasses over andosols, arenosols,
213 phaeozems and regosols, 14.4% by barren and eroded lands over leptosols, regosols and
214 arenosols, 9.3% by grazing over leptosols at lowlands and andosols at midlands, and 0.8% by
215 shrubs and small natural low-bearing forest patches over regosols (FONAG, 2022) (Figure 1e).
216 The PRB hosts two environmentally protected areas: the Cotopaxi National Park and the High
217 Pita Water Conservation Area (Figure 1e).

218 The water-dependent economy in the area includes traditional irrigated crops in small
219 farms and extensive livestock in low-lying areas. Irrigated crops, such as cereals (corn, barley
220 and wheat), potatoes and vegetables, and small fields of rain-fed crops are primarily produced
221 for family consumption. Irrigation water collected from headwater springs in lateral catchments
222 is distributed through a network of ancestral ditches, which favour permanent water loss, soil
223 saturation and preferential infiltration (Somers et al., 2018). Water irrigation demand is around
224 5,000 m³ per hectare yearly (FONAG, 2022).

225

226 3. Methods

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228 3.1. SWAT model

229

230 Hydrological modelling of the PRB was performed using the SWAT (Soil and Water
231 Assessment Tool) extension (Arnold et al., 1998) for the QGIS interface, called QSWAT (Dile
232 et al., 2016). The SWAT model is one of the most widely used hydrological models, and
233 numerous previous studies have demonstrated its capability for modelling rainfall–runoff
234 response in basins of different typologies (Gassman et al., 2007). For example, SWAT has been
235 successfully applied to many non-homogeneous high mountain areas after overcoming the
236 difficulties in determining spatial precipitation with sufficient accuracy, monitoring streamflow,
237 and parameterising land attributes and physical properties from available datasets (Ahl et al.,
238 2008; Jain et al., 2017; Liu et al., 2022; Luo et al., 2012; Senent-Aparicio et al., 2020, 2018,
239 2017). These areas demonstrate similar hydrological complexity and water problems to those
240 existing in the Andean highlands.

241 SWAT is a continuous, long-term, semi-distributed, physically based hydrological
242 model that operates on monthly, daily or hourly time steps. SWAT considers the basin's spatial
243 heterogeneity by dividing it into multiple sub-basins attending to the river network and
244 topography. Sub-basins are further discretised into hydrologic response units (HRUs), unique
245 soil, land-use and slope combinations of homogeneous hydrological responses not identified
246 spatially within a SWAT simulation (Neitsch et al., 2011). The streamflow generated in each
247 HRU adds to the streamflow at the sub-basin outlet, which contributes to observed streamflow
248 at a given reference gauging station downstream (Zhou et al., 2014).

249

250 3.1.1. Input data and model set-up

251

252 The SWAT model requires the following inputs: elevation, land use, soil, vegetation
253 cover and meteorological data such as daily precipitation, maximum and minimum air
254 temperature, solar radiation, relative humidity and wind speed. A 30-m-resolution digital

255 elevation model (DEM) of Ecuador (Datum PSA56) was retrieved from the SavGIS website
 256 (<http://www.savgis.org/ecuador.htm>). Soil information included (i) a soil map (1:50,000 scale)
 257 obtained from MAG-ORSTOM (1978) (Figure 1d), (ii) andosol experimental data obtained
 258 from Lahurette and Recalde (2015), and (iii) the Harmonized World Soil Database (HWSD),
 259 version 1.2 (FAO / UNESCO, 1988). A first comparison of andosol parameters from HWSD
 260 and Lahurette and Recalde (2015) revealed differences in the ± 0.05 range (Table 1). Given this
 261 low relative error, the HWSD was used to characterise each soil type based on information
 262 about soil texture, hydraulic conductivity and available water content, among others. Four soil
 263 types are included in the study area (Table 1). A digital land-use map (scale 1:25,000) was
 264 obtained from CLIRSEN-EMAAP-Q (2006). The primary land use is *páramo* grassland (over
 265 70% of the PRB), followed by barren land (around 15%), as illustrated in Figure 1e.

266 **Table 1.** The Harmonized World Soil Database (FAO / UNESCO, 1988) soil data implemented in the SWAT
 267 model and andosol experimental data obtained from Lahurette and Recalde (2015) in the PRB.

	Andosol					RE ^d	Gleysol	Phaeozem	Regosol
	HWSD	Experimental data ^a					HWSD	HWSD	HWSD
HWSD code ^b / sample ID ^c	16206	s1	s2	s3	s4		16207	16197	16201
Depth, m	0.30	0.40	0.17	0.40	0.36	0.10	0.30	0.30	0.30
Field capacity (FC), mm H ₂ O	150.0	185.6	84.2	198.3	169.7	0.06	150.0	150.0	150.0
Wilting point (WP), mm H ₂ O		134.8	61.1	136.0	147.6				
Saturation (SA), mm H ₂ O		317.2	135.3	289.0	290.7				
pH, H ₂ O	5.1	5.8	5.6	5.7	5.71	0.11		6.20	8.50
Organic carbon, % weight	13.1	15.3	14.5	13.0	14.5	0.08	0.80	0.88	0.34
Bulk density, g cm ³	0.7	0.85	0.76	0.74	0.76	0.13	1.29	1.36	1.29
Sand fraction, %	27	38	40	38	34	0.28	8	60	48
Silt fraction, %	56	43	43	47	55	-0.19	57	31	49
Clay fraction, %	17	19	17	15	11	-0.10	35	9	3

268 ^a Andosol experimental data (ED) obtained from Lahurette and Recalde (2015).

269 ^b Harmonized World Soil Database (HWSD) codes.

270 ^c Sample ID and location as in Figure 1d.

271 ^d For andosol, relative error is expressed as $RE = (ED - HWSD) / ED$; ED is the average value of the
 272 available data.

273

274 Meteorological data (daily precipitation and maximum and minimum air temperature)
 275 for the period 2003–2015 was obtained from public repositories such as Quito's public water
 276 supply company (EPMAPS), Ecuador's Fund for the Protection of Water (FONAG), and
 277 Ecuador's National Institute for Meteorology and Hydrology (INAMHI). These meteorological
 278 stations are located inside and around the PRB (Figure 1b; Table 2). EPMAPS provided the
 279 streamflow data recorded at the Bocatoma gauging station (A1) at the PRB outlet. Among the
 280 options the SWAT model offers in function of available data, the non-global Hargreaves method
 281 (Hargreaves, 1994) was used to estimate potential evapotranspiration.

282 **Table 2.** Description of weather (E) and stream-gauging (A) stations used in this study.

ID	Name	Latitude	Longitude	Elevation (m a.s.l.)	Variable	P ^a	T ^a	Q ^a
E1	Maucatambo	0°40'30" S	78°20'60" W	3,845	P	1,049		
E2	Yangahuagra	0°38'53" S	78°20'24" W	4,040	P	1,053		
E3	Mudadero	0°37'01" S	78°24'07" W	3,866	P, T	721	6.3	

E4	Cotopaxi	0°33'50" S	78°26'35" W	3,670	P, T	941	7.2
E6	Bocatoma	0°29'49" S	78°26'17" W	3,360	P	1,217	
E7	El Carmen	0°30'07" S	78°19'59" W	4,100	T		4.8
E9	Gordillo	0°25'05" S	78°21'25" W	3,248	T		11.5
A1	Bocatoma	0°29'49" S	78°26'08" W	3,380	Q		2.6

ID as in Figure 1b.

^a Average annual values of P—precipitation in mm, T—temperature in °C, and Q—streamflow in m s⁻¹ over the period 2003–2015.

3.1.2. Model calibration and validation

The SWAT model was calibrated using the SUFI-2 algorithm from SWAT-CUP (Calibration and Uncertainty Programs) (Abbaspour, 2007). The calibration methodology used was based on two steps according to Castellanos-Osorio et al. (2023): (i) First, a monthly-scale calibration was conducted with the objective of better adjusting the water volumes, and (ii) subsequently, a second step involved daily-scale calibration to enhance the temporality of the model flows. Twenty-one widely used calibration parameters and their ranges were selected based on SWAT manuals and scientific literature. Three iterations (each iteration representing 500 simulations) were performed to achieve an acceptable calibration. Each parameter range was updated after each iteration. Streamflow data from gauging station A1 for the periods 2006–2010 and 2011–2015 was used for model calibration and validation, respectively. It is important for a reliable calibration and validation of the model that both periods should include dry, wet and usual values (Arnold et al., 2012; Gan et al., 1997). We considered wet and dry years as the 80th and 20th percentiles of annual cumulative precipitation, respectively, resulting in 1228 mm (80th) and 1033 mm (20th). The calibration period (2006–2010) ranged from 1484 mm to 1025 mm, and the validation values (2011–2015) ranged from 1334 mm to 990 mm, thus fulfilling the above premise. The period 2003–2005 was considered for model warm-up.

3.1.3. Model evaluation

The Kling–Gupta efficiency (KGE) (Gupta et al. 2009) was chosen as the primary objective function to evaluate the SWAT model's efficiency on a daily scale. Further efficiency criteria used to measure the model's goodness-of-fit included the logarithmic Nash–Sutcliffe coefficient efficiency (lnNSE) (Nash and Sutcliffe, 1970), the coefficient of determination (R^2), percent bias (PBIAS), root mean squared error (RMSE) and RMSE relative to the standard deviation of the observations (RSR). The description of these statistics can be found in Moriasi et al. (2007). Krause et al. (2005) advise against using the NSE to evaluate low flow conditions. To better evaluate the behavior of low flows, lnNSE has been adopted as an alternative indicator to NSE. The lnNSE has the advantage of providing a more balanced approach at both extremely low and peak values. Previous studies have successfully applied this lnNSE index (Castellanos-Osorio et al. 2023; Chen et al., 2018; Osuch et al., 2018; Parra et al., 2019; Senent-Aparicio et al., 2021a).

3.2. Climate scenarios and statistical bias correction

After the SWAT model was calibrated and validated using current hydrological conditions, streamflow was simulated for future climate scenarios. Data for the different climate change scenarios was collected from the Climate Change Toolkit (CCT) outlined by Vaghefi et al. (2017). Available at the Water Weather Energy Ecosystems website (<http://www.2w2e.com>), the CCT enables data extraction and set-up for climate change studies and hydrological applications. Precipitation and temperature data were extracted from the five GCMs available

329 in the CCT (GFDL-ESM2M, HadGEM2-ES, IPSL-CM5A-LR, MIROC and NoerESM1-M)
 330 for the historical baseline (1975–2005) and the future (2006–2099). The RCP 4.5 and 8.5
 331 emission scenarios were used to assess the potential changes in hydrological response in the
 332 PRB in the mid- (2040–2069) and long-term (2070–2099) future horizons.

333 Climate change scenarios were modelled in four steps. First, historical baseline and
 334 future GCM climate data was extracted from GFDL-ESM2M, HadGEM2-ES, IPSL-CM5A-
 335 LR, MIROC and NoerESM1-M models. Next, the GCM products were regionalised to a
 336 specific area to obtain a meaningful interpretation of the impacts of climate change on a local
 337 scale. In addition, climatic data was corrected to eliminate potential biases (Chen et al., 2013).
 338 Statistical downscaling was used to bias-correct the future GCM data against the observed data.
 339 Different hydro-climatological studies (Vaghefi et al., 2019) consider this statistical bias
 340 correction method satisfactory for downscaling the precipitation and temperature variables
 341 from the GCMs. The CCT software was used for data downloading, spatial downscaling and
 342 correcting the GCMs for bias.

343 The third step was to select GCMs according to their ability to reproduce historical
 344 baseline climatology in the study area. A comparative analysis of GCM products, previously
 345 downscaled and bias corrected, was performed. This task was completed using the methodology
 346 for aquifer recharge projections under future climate change scenarios introduced by Pulido-
 347 Velazquez et al. (2015a). This method compares the monthly means and standard deviations for
 348 an average year of historical and GCM (RCM) precipitation and temperature series over the
 349 same period. For this purpose, the index Id given by Equation 1 measures the goodness-of-fit
 350 obtained for each RCM by adding the changes (increases) in the means and standard deviations
 351 of the control series over the historical period 1980–2004 for both climatic variables:

$$Id_i = \sum_{n,m=1}^2 Id_i(V_n S_m) \quad (1)$$

$$Id_i(V_n S_m) = \sum_{j=1}^{12} [(V_n S_m)_i^j - (V_n S_m)_{Hist}^j] / (V_n S_m)_{Hist}^j,$$

352 where the subscript i denotes a specific RCM, the superscript j represents the months of a mean
 353 year, $V1$ is mean precipitation, $V2$ is mean temperature, and $S1$ and $S2$ are the monthly mean
 354 value and monthly standard deviation for a specific RCMi, respectively.

355 Once the four Id indexes for each RCM were obtained, each corresponding to the mean
 356 value and standard deviation of the precipitation and temperature series, the superior models in
 357 terms of goodness-of-fit to the observed time series were selected. Finally, the simulation results
 358 from the selected RCMs, such as daily precipitation and maximum and minimum air
 359 temperature data for both scenarios, were used as SWAT model inputs to generate the
 360 streamflow responses in the PRB in the mid- and long-term future horizons.

361

362 4. Results and discussion

363

364 4.1. Model calibration and validation

365

366 The SWAT model was calibrated over the period 2006–2010. Twenty-one widely used
 367 calibration parameters and their ranges were selected based on previous knowledge obtained
 368 by authors researching temperate and tropical mountainous areas and numerous examples
 369 compiled from the scientific literature (Jimeno-Sáez et al., 2021; Senent-Aparicio et al., 2021b,
 370 2020). Calibration focused on those parameters associated with groundwater flow, surface and
 371 interflow runoff and soil hydraulics (Table 3). The SWAT parameters were optimised using the
 372 SUFI-2 algorithm SWAT-CUP. The calibration involved two stages: (i) the first thirteen

373 parameters allowed the observed water volume to be conformed, so they were used on a
 374 monthly basis; and (ii) the remaining eight parameters were used to adjust the streamflow
 375 distribution daily. The twenty-one fitted parameters were finally used in the daily model. The
 376 ranges of the calibrated parameters presented in Table 3 have been determined physically
 377 realistic after the criteria proposed by Eckhardt et al. (2005). Therefore, the model can be used
 378 to assess the current hydrological regime in the PRB and predict the impact of future climate
 379 change scenarios on streamflow after formal analysis of the performance metrics.

380 Aside from CN2 and SLSOIL, the most sensitive monthly parameters relate to
 381 groundwater (suffix.gw), especially those associated with the shallow aquifer (GW_REVAP,
 382 GWQMN, GW_DELAY and ALPHA_BF). Similarly, the relevance of soil hydraulics,
 383 vegetation cover, and orography are evident in the PRB, as CN2 emerged as the most influential
 384 parameter by far. This observation is consistent with similar findings concerning the high
 385 sensitivity of other hydrological models based on the Andean highlands to CN2 (Fernandez-
 386 Palomino et al., 2021; Oñate-Valdivieso et al., 2016; Yacoub and Foguet, 2013). The SLSOIL
 387 parameter describes the slope length for lateral subsurface flow (interflow runoff) in an HRU.
 388 The PRB's steep orography makes this parameter highly sensitive due to its significant
 389 dependence on slope (Zaibak and Meddi, 2022). The GW_REVAP parameter indicates the
 390 upward capillary movement of shallow groundwater to the soil when it reaches its driest
 391 condition (i.e., the wilting point). It was calibrated in the 0.02–0.2 range with a fitted value of
 392 0.1, indicating a high rate of groundwater transfer to the soil in drier periods. The parameters
 393 GW_DELAY and GWQMN reflect the delay time for precipitation to reach the shallow aquifer
 394 through the soil profile and the subsequent water depth in the shallow aquifer measured from
 395 the surface, respectively. As deduced, the contribution of groundwater to streamflow in the PRB
 396 is only possible when the water depth in the shallow aquifer is equal to or greater than GWQMN
 397 (Sharma et al., 2022). Furthermore, the baseflow amount is directly related to GWQMN
 398 (Kannan et al., 2007). Although the water depth in the shallow aquifer was 129.5 mm, the 58.6-
 399 day delay time is close to the maximum range, reflecting the soils' high storage capacity, and
 400 the high potential for baseflow. In the PRB, 60% of the soils are andosols with a WRC \geq 0.5
 401 (Figure 1d). The parameter ALPHA_BF concerns aquifer recharge mechanisms and subsequent
 402 time-delayed aquifer discharge contributing to streamflow (Oñate-Valdivieso and Bosque-
 403 Sendra, 2014). The fitted value is 0.63 day⁻¹, indicating a moderate discharge response to
 404 aquifer recharge events. Regarding the daily calibrated parameters, the most sensitive are
 405 OV_N, CH_S1, SLSUBBSN and HRU_SLP, in this order. All the parameters determine the
 406 concentration time and average velocity (Singh and Jha, 2021), which define the hydrograph's
 407 shape (Athira and Sudheer, 2021).

408 **Table 3.** Calibration of the SWAT model parameters.

Parameter ^a	Description and units ^b	Range used in calibration	Fitted value
r_CN2.mgt	SCS runoff curve number	–0.1 to 0.1	0.02
v_ALPHA_BF.gw	Baseflow alpha factor (day ⁻¹)	0 to 0.8	0.63
a_GW_DELAY.gw	Groundwater delay time (day)	–10 to 70	58.60
a_GWQMN.gw	Threshold depth of water in the shallow aquifer for return flow to occur (mm)	–200 to 200	129.50
v_GW_REVAP.gw	Groundwater revap coefficient	0.02 to 0.2	0.10
a_RCHRG_DP.gw	Deep aquifer percolation fraction	–0.01 to 0.03	–0.004
a_REVAPMN.gw	Threshold depth of water in the shallow aquifer for revap or percolation to the deep aquifer to occur (mm)	–250 to 250	185.60
v_CANMX.hru	Maximum canopy storage (mm)	0 to 5	0.15
v_EPCO.bsn	Plant uptake compensation factor	0.3 to 1	0.45

v_ESCO.bsn	Soil evaporation compensation factor	0.3 to 0.8	0.71
r_SOL_AWC.sol	Available water capacity of the soil layer (mm) H ₂ O/mm soil	-0.02 to 0.02	-0.01
v_LAT_TTIME.hru	Lateral flow travel time (day)	10 to 150	104.01
v_SLSOIL.hru	Slope length for lateral subsurface flow (m)	0 to 50	0.28
r_SLSUBBSN.hru	Average slope length (m)	-0.1 to 0.5	0.41
r_HRU_SLP.hru	Average slope steepness (m/m)	-0.5 to 0.2	0.04
v_OV_N.hru	Manning's (n) value for overland flow	0.1 to 1	0.99
r_CH_S1.sub	Average slope of tributary channels (m/m)	-0.5 to 0.2	-0.48
v_CH_N1.sub	Manning's (n) value for the tributary channels	0.01 to 30	2.08
r_CH_S2.rte	Average slope of main channel along the channel length (m/m)	-0.5 to 0.3	-0.21
v_CH_N2.rte	Manning's (n) value for the main channel	0.02 to 0.2	0.13
v_SURLAG.bsn	Surface runoff lag coefficient	0.05 to 15	3.74

409 ^a Parameter notation as it appears in SWAT manuals. Prefix r_ refers to relative change (i.e., the current parameter
410 must be multiplied by 1 + the value obtained in calibration), Prefix v_ means that the existing parameter value
411 must be replaced by the value obtained in calibration, and Prefix a_ refers to absolute change (i.e., the fitted value
412 must be added to the existing parameter value).

413 ^b Units are only included for dimensional parameters; the remaining parameters are dimensionless.

414

415 Figure 2 compares simulated streamflow values with their observed counterparts during
416 daily (Figure 2a) and monthly (Figure 2b) calibration and validation. The SWAT model
417 generally simulated trends and baseflow well but failed to capture peak flow magnitudes. These
418 differences are much more evident on a daily basis (Figure 2a); the SWAT model has evidently
419 underestimated peaks above 7 m³ s⁻¹. This may be caused by the fact that SWAT uses the CN-
420 SCS method to calculate runoff and this method cannot model snowmelt adequately for
421 mountainous regions (such as the area of this study). This limitation has been reported in
422 numerous studies in different regions worldwide (Gassman et al., 2014; Jimeno-Sáez et al.,
423 2018; Liu et al., 2022; López-Ballesteros et al., 2020; Ur Rahman et al., 2020), and SWAT
424 developers still have much to do (Arnold et al., 2012). However, this limitation does not
425 substantially affect the groundwater components evaluation, which is the subject of this paper.

426

Figure 2. In the PRB over the period 2006–2015, hydrograph simulated using the SWAT model and compared with the observed streamflow on (a) a daily and (b) a monthly basis. Calibration (2006–2010) and validation (2011–2015) periods are also displayed.

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Monthly model calibration resulted in good agreement between simulated and observed streamflow, as indicated by the evaluation statistics given in Table 4. All the evaluation statistics in the monthly streamflow comparison outperformed the equivalent metrics in daily streamflow comparisons. The KGE is based on the decomposition of NSE into correlation, bias and relative variability (Rivas-Tabares et al., 2019). However, it demonstrates less sensitivity to high streamflow values after considering all streamflow levels in a more balanced approach (Radcliffe and Mukundan, 2017). According to Knoben et al. (2019), KGE values below -0.41 should be considered unacceptable, whereas good performance is achieved when $KGE > 0.5$ (Ekolu et al., 2022). Except for the daily calibration in which $KGE = 0.48$, on the threshold of a good model, the other daily and monthly results indicate satisfactory SWAT model performance. Logarithmic NSE ($\ln NSE$) was used instead of NSE to assess the model's performance regarding low flows (Cheng et al., 2020) since the former reduces sensitivity to peak flows (Krause et al., 2005). As with the KGE, the 0.44 daily calibration value indicates acceptable performance, although the daily and monthly validation results are above 0.5, indicating satisfactory model fitting (Cheng et al., 2017). The R^2 explains the fraction of variance in observed values in the model. Similar to NSE, R^2 is also moderately sensitive to high flows since it can be significantly affected by outliers, increasing model bias (Legates and McCabe Jr., 1999). Peak flow underestimation could be one reason for daily R^2 values below 0.5 in calibration and validation. Since flow aggregation produces peak flattening, the monthly R^2 values are

452 slightly higher than 0.6 in calibration and validation, indicating satisfactory model
 453 performance (Moriasi et al., 2015).

454

455 **Table 4.** SWAT model evaluation statistics for daily and monthly streamflow.

Model evaluation statistic	Daily streamflow		Monthly streamflow	
	Calibration	Validation	Calibration	Validation
KGE	0.48	0.60	0.73	0.65
lnNSE	0.44	0.52	0.67	0.65
R ²	0.31	0.45	0.66	0.67
PBIAS	1.96	7.43	1.75	7.36
RMSE	1.25	0.95	0.51	0.58
RSR	0.85	0.77	0.58	0.62

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457 PBIAS checks the model's tendency to overestimate (PBIAS > 0) or underestimate
 458 (PBIAS < 0) the observed values (Gupta et al., 1999). The daily and monthly results prove to
 459 be somewhat similar. Based on Moriasi et al. (2015), the model's performance was very good
 460 during calibration and good during validation, with an overestimation of less than 8% on a daily
 461 and monthly basis. Finally, RMSE and RSR measure the difference between observed and
 462 simulated streamflow, although RMSE measures the absolute difference, and RSR standardises
 463 the difference by dividing RMSE by the standard deviation of the observations (Moriasi et al.,
 464 2007). Despite their different conceptions and interpretations, both statistics point in the same
 465 direction. According to Singh et al. (2005), the difference between observed and simulated
 466 streamflow can be considered low when RMSE is less than half of the standard deviation of the
 467 observations. Table 4 demonstrates that the daily RMSE is two-fold the value obtained monthly.
 468 Since the daily RSR values are higher than 0.75, the model can be considered unsatisfactory
 469 (Kalin et al., 2010; Moriasi et al., 2015, 2007). Notwithstanding, the monthly model performed
 470 in the good-to-satisfactory range during calibration (RSR = 0.58) and validation (RSR = 0.62),
 471 respectively.

472 Statistical analysis revealed limited SWAT model performance on the daily basis, as
 473 pointed out previously by Reza Eini et al. (2020). However, the monthly results demonstrate
 474 reasonably good prediction capability, permitting further model processing as it is considered
 475 in previous studies all over the world (Tan et al., 2021). Moreover, the monthly time resolution
 476 is considered sufficiently competent for long-term water resource evaluation and subsequent
 477 long-term climate impact forecasting (Georgakakos et al., 2012), which is the subject of this
 478 paper.

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480 4.2. Selection of climate change models

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482 As described in Section 3.2, the five RCM models available in the CCT (GFDL-
 483 ESM2M, HadGEM2-ES, IPSL-CM5A-LR, MIROC and NoerESM1-M) were analysed to
 484 identify those that best reproduce the average year from the mean values and standard
 485 deviations. The selection was based on the *Id* index, which is the sum of the absolute value of
 486 the relative differences in the historical and control series statistics during the 12 months of an
 487 average year. Table 5 presents the *Id* values obtained for the 2006–2015 study period. The
 488 higher the *Id*, the worse the goodness-of-fit. Except for the HadGEM2-ES model, the RCM
 489 models achieved similar mean *Id* values, *Id*(Δx), for precipitation and temperature. However,
 490 greater differences in standard deviations, *Id*($\Delta \sigma$), were observed among the RCM models,
 491 especially for temperature, which ranged from 18.78 (model IPSL-CM5A-LR) to 55.64 (model
 492 GFDL-ESM2M). The IPSL-CM5A-LR, MIROC and NoerESM1-M models achieved lower *Id*
 493 values. This issue is in line with previous similar works (Pulido-Velazquez et al., 2015b; Urrutia

494 and Vuille, 2009). Hence, these three RCM models were selected to assess the impact of climate
 495 change on renewable groundwater resources in the PRB.

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Table 5. Id index of each RCM model for precipitation and temperature, monthly series.

RCM model	Precipitation		Temperature		Id^a
	$Id(\Delta x)$	$Id(\Delta \sigma)$	$Id(\Delta x)$	$Id(\Delta \sigma)$	
1 GFDL-ESM2M	0.87	11.60	0.61	55.64	68.72
2 HadGEM2-ES	7.97	12.24	7.47	23.12	50.80
3 IPSL-CM5A-LR	0.80	5.92	0.61	18.78	26.11
4 MIROC	1.22	6.10	0.57	30.32	38.21
5 NoerESM1-M	0.92	8.38	0.59	22.65	32.54

498 ^a Id —sum of the absolute values of the mean values, denoted as $Id(\Delta x)$, and standard deviations, denoted as $Id(\Delta \sigma)$,
 499 of precipitation and temperature monthly series.

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501 4.3. Changes in projected precipitation and temperature

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503 The implemented ensembles consisted of three RCM models (IPSL-CM5A-LR,
 504 MIROC and NoerESM1-M) and RCP emission scenarios 4.5 and 8.5. Table 6 summarises the
 505 changes in the average values and standard deviations of the temperature and precipitation (the
 506 climate variables) annual series from the implemented ensembles relative to the corresponding
 507 values of each RCM baseline period (1976–2005). The changes refer to the mid- (2040–2069)
 508 and long-term (2070–2099) future horizons. In addition, the distributions of monthly mean
 509 values and standard deviations of temperature and precipitation for the three RCM-RCP 4.5
 510 ensembles and the three RCM-RCP 8.5 ensembles over the baseline period in the mid- and
 511 long-term future horizons are displayed in Figures 3 and 4, respectively.

512 Regarding average annual temperature (Table 6), the three RCMs predicted increases
 513 from +1.4°C, in the mid-term, to +2.5°C, in the long term, for RCP 4.5 and from +1.9°C, in the
 514 mid-term, to 4.7°C, in the long term, for RCP 8.5. These figures indicate increases of +20–35%
 515 for RCP 4.5 and +30–65% for RCP 8.5 regarding the baseline. The NoerESM1-M model
 516 predicted lower temperature increases regarding the baseline, with values 10–20% (depending
 517 on the RCP) lower than those obtained in the other two RCMs. This increase in temperature is
 518 a proven historical fact corroborated by the 0.1–0.2°C increase per decade recorded in the last
 519 70–100 years (Buytaert et al., 2014; Sklenář et al., 2021; Vuille et al., 2015), which exceeds the
 520 threshold of natural climate variation (Gutiérrez-Salazar and Medrano-Vizcaíno, 2019). These
 521 results concur with the average temperature increases of 2°C and 5°C predicted in the coastal
 522 versant of the WAC (Ilbay-Yupa et al., 2021; Rivadeneira-Vera et al., 2020) and the Andean
 523 highlands (Herzog et al., 2012) of Ecuador, respectively. Regarding the average annual
 524 temperature standard deviations, the IPSL-CM5A-LR and NoerESM1-M models revealed
 525 changes lower than the baseline for RCP 4.5, whereas the MIROC model predicted increases
 526 of more than 100% for RCP 4.5. The RCP 8.5 ensembles predicted an increase in temperature
 527 in the 20–90% range, depending on the RCM.

528 At the monthly scale, for RCP 4.5 (Figure 3) and RCP 8.5 (Figure 4), the mid- and long-
 529 term mean temperature trends are similar to the baseline, regardless of the RCM considered.
 530 Only the NoerESM1-M model predicted more pronounced variation between April and July for
 531 RCP 8.5 in the long term, with higher temperature increases for the rest of the year. However,
 532 the standard deviations for monthly temperature changed significantly depending on the RCM-
 533 RCP ensemble. While the baseline remained unvaried in the mid- and long-term RCP 4.5
 534 scenarios, except for the MIROC model, RCP 8.5 revealed an apparent increase in standard
 535 deviations for all the RCMs, especially in the long term. Moreover, the dry season exhibited the
 536 highest values, except in the NoerESM1-M model. Furthermore, the change in temperature for
 537 RCP 4.5 is much greater in the mid-term than in the long term, inversely compared to the RCP

538 8.5 results. Generally, these projections are consistent with the results previously assessed in
 539 similar regions studies (Buytaert et al., 2011; Cresso et al., 2020; Flores-López et al., 2016a).
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 542 **Figure 3.** Distribution of the mean values and standard deviations of monthly temperature and precipitation of the
 543 three RCM-RCP 4.5 ensembles for the baseline period (1976–2005) and the mid- (2040–2069) and long-term
 544 (2070–2099) future horizons.
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Figure 4. Distribution of the RCP 8.5 ensembles for the baseline period (1976–2005) and the mid- (2040–2069) and long-term (2070–2099) future horizons.

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Regarding average annual precipitation (Table 6), the MIROC–RCP 4.5 ensemble revealed slight decreases of -2% and -1% in the mid- and long-term horizons, respectively, compared to the baseline. Conversely, the ensembles generated from the other two RCMs predicted increases. Unlike the temperature trend, precipitation covered a wide range of changes regarding the baseline, varying from +0.4% to +41% depending on the RCM-RCP ensemble, although RCP 8.5 generally demonstrated greater increases. Recent studies agree that regional warming is more evident than future variations in precipitation. For example, several authors have demonstrated a decrease of nearly 15% in the IAV region (Kirtman et al., 2013; Vuille et al., 2008), while others have suggested increases of around 10% in the eastern and western flanks (Ilbay-Yupa et al., 2021). Historical precipitation over the last 50 years does not display a definitive trend (Vuille et al., 2003), only a slight reduction at most (Martínez et al., 2011)

562 with few impacts on water resource availability. Regarding the average annual precipitation
563 standard deviation, the changes vary between -20% and +35%, in contrast to the wide variation
564 between -30% and +110% in the average annual temperature standard deviation.
565 Notwithstanding, each RCM-RCP ensemble differs significantly. The IPSL-CM5A-LR model
566 demonstrated a significant decrease (-22%) for RCP 4.5 in the long term but the opposite (an
567 increase of +15%) for RCP 8.5. The NoerESM1-M model achieved increases of approximately
568 20% for all the scenarios, whereas the MIROC model revealed precipitation increases and
569 decreases depending on the RCP and time horizon considered.

570 At the monthly scale, for RCP 4.5 (Figure 3) and RCP 8.5 (Figure 4), mean precipitation
571 also exhibits slight seasonal differences. For all RCMs, mean monthly precipitation is similar
572 to the baseline, except in June. This finding is especially relevant for RCP 8.5 in the long term,
573 where the increase reached +100% in the IPSL-CM5A-LR and MIROC models. No clear trends
574 are evident concerning the monthly precipitation standard deviation since variations are
575 indistinctly positive or negative depending on the RCM-RCP ensemble, which appear not to be
576 in line with Zhiña et al. (2019) whose study in the southern Ecuadorian Andes points to a higher
577 increase in monthly precipitation, especially in the long-term period.

578 In the mid- and long-term future, the increase in average temperature combined with the
579 slight increase in average precipitation obtained in most of the RCM-RCP ensembles should
580 result in higher actual evapotranspiration (i.e., the evaporative fraction of precipitation that
581 returns to the atmosphere) and, therefore, a decrease in available water for ecosystems and
582 human uses (i.e., the non-evaporative fraction of precipitation or the water amount that could
583 contribute to streamflow and aquifer recharge after discounting transmission losses), as
584 presented in Table 6. This plausible framework could also be accompanied by changes in the
585 fire regime (Kitzberger et al., 2022) due to warmer temperatures and soil degradation resulting
586 from subsequent low-vegetated patches and changes in the frequency and intensity of rainfall
587 events (Muñoz et al., 2021) and dry spells. This combination could worsen the current hydraulic
588 state of andosols (Young et al., 2011), altering or degrading the *páramo* ecosystem's
589 hydrological functioning and temporal water storage capacity. This alpine ecosystem's
590 sensitivity to climate change (Cuesta et al., 2017) implies a high risk of habitat loss and unsafe
591 water provision, as identified by Anderson et al. (2011).

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Table 6. Changes in the average values and standard deviations of annual precipitation and temperature predicted by the implemented RCM-RCP ensembles relative to the corresponding values for each RCM's baseline scenario.

RCM model	Emission scenario	Period	Annual precipitation (mm)				Annual temperature (°C)			
			Mean value	Change relative to baseline ^a	Standard deviation	Change relative to baseline ^a	Mean value	Change relative to baseline ^a	Standard deviation	Change relative to baseline ^a
IPSL-CM5A-LR	Baseline	1976–2005	1091.29	–	91.2	–	7.12	–	0.45	–
	RCP 4.5	2040–2069	1124.11	+ 32.82(+3%)	95.06	+3.88(+4%)	9.08	+1.96(+28%)	0.31	–0.14(–31%)
		2070–2099	1143.73	+52.45(+5%)	71.50	–19.68(–22%)	9.55	+2.43(+34%)	0.27	–0.18(–39%)
	RCP 8.5	2040–2069	1141.76	+50.47(+5%)	84.40	–6.78(–7%)	9.82	+2.71 (+38%)	0.53	+0.08(+18%)
		2070–2099	1309.72	+218.43 (+20%)	104.57	+13.39(+15%)	11.82	+4.70 (+66%)	0.69	+0.24(+54%)
	MIROC	Baseline	1976–2005	945.32	–	49.18	–	8.20	–	0.47
RCP 4.5		2040–2069	923.21	–22.12 (–2%)	44.34	–4.84(–10%)	10.03	+1.83 (+22%)	1.00	+0.53(+111%)
		2070–2099	932.08	–13.24 (–1%)	46.16	–3.02(–6%)	10.67	+2.47 (+30%)	0.67	+0.20(+41%)
RCP 8.5		2040–2069	948.82	+3.50 (+0.4%)	66.72	+17.54(36%)	10.69	+2.48 (+30%)	0.61	+0.14(+29%)
		2070–2099	1052.05	+106.73 (+11%)	39.27	–9.91(–20%)	12.70	+4.50 (+55%)	0.89	+0.42(+88%)
NoerESM1-M		Baseline	1976–2005	970.43	–	70.20	–	7.16	–	0.33
	RCP 4.5	2040–2069	1160.21	+189.79(+20%)	89.38	+19.18(+27%)	8.53	+1.37 (+19%)	0.29	–0.04(–13%)
		2070–2099	1149.02	+178.59 (+18%)	86.31	+16.11(+23%)	8.84	+1.68 (+23%)	0.27	–0.06(–19%)
	RCP 8.5	2040–2069	1197.85	+227.42 (+23%)	89.81	+19.61(+28%)	9.02	+1.86 (+26%)	0.40	+0.07(+22%)
		2070–2099	1371.91	+401.48 (+41%)	92.55	+22.34(+32%)	10.28	+3.12 (+44%)	0.46	+0.13(+40%)

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^a Changes are expressed as positive or negative absolute (in the same unit as the variable) and relative (percentages in parentheses) differences.

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4.4. Water resources response to climate change

600 This section analyses and discusses the main water balance components' response to
601 each RCM-RCP ensemble in the mid- (2040–2069) and long-term (2070–2099) future horizons.
602 The results are summarised in Table 7. The changes in the baseline scenario indicate the
603 renewable groundwater resource's expected magnitude and hydrological significance in the
604 future. Different experimental relationships for aquifer recharge predictions under different
605 precipitation fields associated to current and future climate frameworks can be found in the
606 scientific literature (Alcalá et al., 2018, 2011; Ross et al., 2005). For example, Taylor et al.
607 (2013) observed a positive relationship between projected changes in precipitation and
608 subsequent aquifer recharge responses. In the PRB, although increased precipitation typically
609 implies increased streamflow, it does not always correspond with increased aquifer recharge,
610 as presented in Table 7. Therefore, precipitation (P) and aquifer recharge (TA_RCHG) did not
611 follow a linear relationship, and more interdisciplinary information to conceptualise the soil–
612 aquifer relationships is needed to interpret the changes in lower aquifer recharge rates obtained
613 as differences in P and other significant water balance components such as actual
614 evapotranspiration (ET). In most ungauged mountainous areas, ET is typically one of the less
615 certain water balance components, especially when only non-global models, such as Hargreaves
616 (1994) and others, can be used due to data scarcity (Alcalá et al., 2011; España et al., 2013,
617 2011; Were et al., 2007). This is the case in the PRB, where uncertainty in ET propagates
618 through the model equations to reveal relatively uncertain aquifer recharge rates, which can be
619 uninterpretable when attempting to draw conclusions. Therefore, comparisons of aquifer
620 recharge with the evaporative fraction of P (ET:P ratio) or the non-evaporative fraction of P (1–
621 [ET:P] ratio) instead of P or ET were preferred to analysing changes in streamflow and aquifer
622 recharge. Likewise, other authors (Pool et al., 2021; Seddon et al., 2021) have used similar
623 indices in order to provide more accurate relationships between the parameters implied in the
624 aquifer recharge. When the ET:P and 1–(ET:P) ratios were compared with aquifer recharge,
625 interpretable negative and positive relationships were obtained, respectively, as expected.

626 After this conceptualisation, the IPSL-CM5A-LR model produced increases lower than
627 6% in P and ET for the two RCPs. The exception is RCP 8.5 in the long term, which reached
628 increases of +20% and +15% in P and ET, respectively. Similar P and ET magnitudes resulted
629 in slight increases in the ET:P ratio below +2%, contributing to a gradual increase in streamflow
630 due to the increase in P but a sharp decrease in aquifer recharge of between -14% and -17%. In
631 the long term, RCP 8.5 significantly increased P (+20%) and ET (+15%). However, the greater
632 difference in P and ET increased the 1–(ET:P) ratio by +6%, resulting in significant increases
633 in streamflow (+27%) and aquifer recharge (+15%). The NoerESM1-M model produced higher
634 increases in P and ET, significantly increasing the 1–(ET:P) ratio compared with the other two
635 RCMs, reaching +25% for RCP 8.5 in the long term. Moreover, the NoerESM1-M model
636 increased aquifer recharge; the observed aquifer recharge increase is two-fold higher than the
637 observed streamflow increase. In fact, the increase in streamflow and aquifer recharge for RCP
638 8.5 in the long term is +76% and +173%, respectively. The MIROC model illustrates how the
639 water balance components adjust when P decreases and ET increases. Regarding the IPSL-
640 CM5A-LR model, the ET:P ratios are also positive (in the 1–2% range), but the other water
641 balance components differ substantially. The decrease in P caused a slight decrease in
642 streamflow (between -3% and -6%), but the diminution of aquifer recharge was significant at
643 approximately -40% for RCP 4.5 in the long term.

644 The distributions of the monthly mean values of the water balance components for the
645 three RCM-RCP 4.5 ensembles and the three RCM-RCP 8.5 ensembles, over the baseline
646 period and the mid- and long-term future horizons, are displayed in Figures 5 and 6,

647 respectively. The variations in monthly aquifer recharge are highly dependent on the RCP. For
648 RCP 4.5, aquifer recharge decreased conspicuously in the mid and long term, except in the
649 NoerESM1-M model. However, RCP 8.5 revealed a significant increase, especially in the
650 second half of the year. The differences in streamflow and aquifer recharge in the NoerESM1-
651 M model increased significantly, especially in the long term. Notwithstanding, the yearly
652 pattern does not differ significantly from the baseline, except in June and July (dry season), as
653 previously identified in monthly variations in temperature and precipitation (climate variables).
654 No significant differences were observed in the average monthly ET:P and 1-(ETP:P) ratios.
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656
657 **Figure 5.** Distribution of the monthly mean values of the main water balance components predicted by the three
658 RCM-RCP 4.5 ensembles in the PRB for the baseline period (1976–2005) and the mid- (2040–2069) and long-
659 term (2070–2099) future horizons. P—precipitation (mm); ET—evapotranspiration (mm); ET/P—evaporative
660 fraction of P as a dimensionless fraction; 1-(ET/P)—non-evaporative fraction of P as a dimensionless fraction;
661 WYLD—maximum amount of water that can contribute to streamflow and aquifer recharge after discounting
662 transmission losses (mm); and TA_RCHG—total aquifer recharge (mm).

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Figure 6. Distribution of the monthly mean values of the main water balance components predicted by the three RCM-RCP 8.5 ensembles in the PRB for the baseline period (1976–2005) and the mid- (2040–2069) and long-term (2070–2099) future horizons. P—precipitation (mm); ET—evapotranspiration (mm); ET/P—evaporative fraction of P as a dimensionless fraction; 1-(ET/P)—non-evaporative fraction of P as a dimensionless fraction; WYLD—maximum amount of water that can contribute to streamflow and aquifer recharge after discounting transmission losses (mm); and TA_RCHG—total aquifer recharge (mm).

670 **Table 7.** Average annual SWAT water balance components in the PRB after implementing the RCM-RCP 4.5 and 8.5 ensembles for mid- (2040–2069) and long-term
671 (2070–2099) future horizons.

RCM model	Emission scenario	Period	P (mm) ^a	ET (mm) ^a	ET/P ^a	1–(ET/P) ^a	WYLD (mm) ^a	TA_RCHG (mm) ^a
IPSL-CM5A-LR	Baseline	1976–2005	1091.29	663.57	0.61	0.39	412.23	17.54
	RCP 4.5	2040–2069	1124.11 (+3%)	695.19 (+5%)	0.62 (+2%)	0.38 (-3%)	414.31 (+1%)	14.59 (-17%)
		2070–2099	1143.73 (+5%)	701.92 (+6%)	0.61 (+1%)	0.39 (-1%)	427.89 (+4%)	14.98 (-15%)
	RCP 8.5	2040–2069	1141.76 (+5%)	701.21 (+6%)	0.61 (+1%)	0.39 (-2%)	428.34 (+4%)	15.05 (-14%)
		2070–2099	1309.72 (+20%)	765.56 (+15%)	0.58 (-4%)	0.42 (+6%)	523.92 (+27%)	20.11 (+15%)
	MIROC	Baseline	1976–2005	945.32	657.08	0.70	0.30	283.64
RCP 4.5		2040–2069	923.21 (-2%)	651.27 (-1%)	0.71 (+1%)	0.29 (-3%)	267.72 (-6%)	3.08 (-24%)
		2070–2099	932.08 (-1%)	660.99 (+1%)	0.71 (+2%)	0.29 (-5%)	267.93 (-6%)	2.44 (-40%)
RCP 8.5		2040–2069	948.82 (+0.4%)	669.39 (+2%)	0.71 (+1%)	0.29 (-3%)	275.03 (-3%)	2.86 (-29%)
		2070–2099	1052.05 (+11%)	719.31 (+9%)	0.68 (-2%)	0.32 (+4%)	327.44 (+15%)	4.70 (+16%)
NoerESM1-M		Baseline	1976–2005	970.43	628.23	0.65	0.35	332.88
	RCP 4.5	2040–2069	1160.21 (+20%)	693.67 (+10%)	0.60 (-8%)	0.40 (+14%)	452.19 (+36%)	15.72 (+82%)
		2070–2099	1149.02 (+18%)	697.14 (+11%)	0.61 (-6%)	0.39 (+12%)	436.94 (+31%)	14.09 (+63%)
	RCP 8.5	2040–2069	1197.85 (+23%)	711.10 (+13%)	0.59 (-8%)	0.41 (+15%)	469.32 (+41%)	16.06 (+86%)
		2070–2099	1371.91 (+41%)	765.57 (+22%)	0.56 (-14%)	0.44 (+25%)	585.90 (+76%)	23.54 (+173%)

672 ^a P—average annual precipitation; ET—average annual evapotranspiration; ET/P—evaporative fraction of P as a dimensionless fraction; 1–(ET/P)—non-evaporative fraction
673 of P as a dimensionless fraction; WYLD—average annual maximum amount of water that can contribute to streamflow and aquifer recharge after discounting transmission
674 losses; and TA_RCHG—average annual total aquifer recharge. The percentages of the relative changes in the variables and/or ratios to the corresponding baseline scenarios are
675 given in parentheses.
676

These findings demonstrate a strong positive relationship between P and streamflow. However, aquifer recharge variations are predominantly related to the ET:P and 1–(ET:P) ratios. This observation supports the rationale that aquifer recharge highly depends on the water available after soil and vegetation water demands have been satisfied (Bhunias, 2020); in the case of andosols is high as described above. The logical increases in streamflow for low (below +10%) increases in precipitation are also corroborated by streamflow increases in the 1–3% range for every +1% change in P, as reported globally by Chiew et al. (2006). However, uncertainty propagation in model projections has induced a wide range of aquifer recharge changes, as discussed above and observed by Döll (2009). Notably, small changes in aquifer recharge forecasted by Buytaert et al. (2010) in equivalent humid Andean highlands with similar andosols do not align with our results indicating changes ranging from -40% to +173%. This disparity is not definitive since it can be attributed to a number of factors, such as the different observation scales used, improbability of RCM models over time, and inadequate aquifer recharge estimation as differences in P and ET when data scarcity prevents ET estimation using global models (Alcalá et al., 2011; España et al., 2013, 2011; Were et al., 2007).

As indicated in Table 8 and Figures 5 and 6, variation in aquifer recharge is greater in the wet season (February to May) than in the dry season (July to September), except in the MIROC model. In the IPSL-CM5A-LR and NoerESM1-M models, aquifer recharge in the dry season is approximately 0.7–0.9-fold the observations during the wet season. However, the magnitude of the relative change in aquifer recharge in wet and dry seasons differs; the change in the wet season is usually greater than that observed in the dry season. This typical aquifer recharge behaviour depends on available soil water, as has been documented in other mountainous areas (Alcalá et al., 2011; Were et al., 2007). However, a discrepancy is observed in the MIROC model: the change is between -15% and -54% in the wet season and between -9% and +47% in the dry season. Similarly, the sharp increases in aquifer recharge in the NoerESM1-M model are much higher in the wet season than in the dry season. Aquifer recharge rates are typically low, in the 0.43–8.38 mm range. Null groundwater exploitation in the moderate-permeability volcanic and volcano-sedimentary aquifers in the PRB favours high piezometric levels. Hence the aquifer can be considered virtually full, repelling most recharge events, while most soil water excess percolates downwards and contributes interflow runoff to streamflow in the wet season. Consequently, only a minor fraction of the soil water excess during the wet season produces aquifer recharge, delayed, to some extent, when the aquifer marginally empties during the dry season.

Table 8. Seasonal distribution of predicted aquifer recharge (TA_RCHG) in the PRB after implementing the RCM-RCP 4.5 and 8.5 ensembles for mid- (2040–2069) and long-term (2070–2099) future horizons.

RCM model	Emission scenario	Period	TA_RCHG (mm) ^a	TA_RCHG (wet season fraction, mm) ^a	TA_RCHG (dry season fraction, mm) ^a
IPSL-CM5A-LR	Baseline	1976–2005	17.54	6.97	4.76
	RCP 4.5	2040–2069	14.59 (-17%)	4.99 (-28%)	4.49 (-6%)
		2070–2099	14.98 (-15%)	5.61 (-19%)	4.30 (-10%)
	RCP 8.5	2040–2069	15.05 (-14%)	4.93 (-29%)	4.61 (-3%)
		2070–2099	20.11 (+15%)	6.35 (-9%)	6.14 (+29%)
	MIROC	Baseline	1976–2005	4.05	0.93
RCP 4.5		2040–2069	3.08 (-24%)	0.51 (-46%)	1.44 (-9%)
		2070–2099	2.44 (-40%)	0.79 (-15%)	1.16 (-26%)
RCP 8.5		2040–2069	2.86 (-29%)	0.43 (-54%)	1.35 (-14%)
		2070–2099	4.70 (+16%)	0.61 (-35%)	2.31 (+47%)
NoerESM1-M		Baseline	1976–2005	8.62	2.77

RCP 4.5	2040–2069	15.72 (+82%)	5.21 (+88%)	4.47 (+73%)
	2070–2099	14.09 (+63%)	4.96 (+79%)	3.88 (+50%)
RCP 8.5	2040–2069	16.06 (+86%)	5.65 (+104%)	4.32 (+67%)
	2070–2099	23.54 (+173%)	8.38 (+203%)	6.13 (+137%)

^a Changes are expressed as positive or negative absolute (in the same unit as the variable) and relative (percentages in parentheses) differences.

Previous studies conducted over a large territory including soils with worse hydraulic conditions (less water storage capacity) in nearby regions (Carvajal et al., 2017) highlight the apparent differences between wet and dry seasons. However, our results in the PRB (where andosols with better hydraulic conditions predominate) do not diverge as much by season. In fact, soil hydraulics tests performed on degraded and well-preserved andosols (Boulangier et al., 2007; Buytaert et al., 2009) also provide different aquifer recharge responses, which diverge from the more similar responses obtained in the implemented RCM-RCP 4.5 and 8.5 ensemble projections. The exception is the NoerESM1-M model projections, which could depend more on specific soil, vegetation cover and climate data for improved results. However, this work is beyond the scope of this study.

The influence of the soil preservation state on aquifer recharge response appears evident. Alcalá (2016) used tracer (chemical, stable isotopes and radioisotopes) and physical techniques to evaluate aquifer recharge in a close IAV catchment with well-preserved andosols over moderate-permeability volcano-sedimentary geological formations (the typical *páramo* ecosystem landscape) similar to those existing in the PRB. This author demonstrated aquifer recharge responses in the three–four-month range after the wet season had ended. Therefore, the soil preservation degree is a determinant for the ET:P and 1–(ET:P) ratios and, thus, controls the magnitude and duration of aquifer recharge events. Climate change could alter (deteriorate) soil hydraulic properties, as reported by Kumar et al. (2022) and, therefore, current surface water–groundwater dynamics in the andosol-dominated Andean highlands, resulting in less soil water storage capacity, more rapid runoff responses and prolonged water-deficit periods.

The magnitude and variability of water resources are critical for conserving natural biodiversity and the stability of aquatic environments (Pérez-Sánchez et al., 2020). The indicators of hydrological alteration included in the IAHRIS (IndicAtors of Hydrological alteration in RIverS) software (Fernández et al., 2012), specific for the evaluation of the alteration of the natural regime of a river in non-coetaneous series, have been used to evaluate the impact of climate change on the magnitude, variability and seasonality of water resources in the PRB. These indexes are: 1) Mean value of the annual volumes (Mean); 2) Extreme variability (EV), which is calculated as the average value of the difference between the maximum and minimum monthly discharge for each year; 3) Difference between the daily mean flows corresponding to the 10th (Q10) and 90th (Q90) percentiles; 4) Maximum/minimum relative frequency of the month (MaxRF/MinRF). As can be seen in table 9, there is no significant overall increase in annual flows except in the long term and under the scenario RCP 8.5. Only the RCM Model NoerESM1-M estimates significant increases in annual flows in the short and long term and for RCP 4.5 and 8.5. However, there is a wider consensus in estimating an increase in flow variability. For example, all models estimate that the extreme variability may almost double in the long term and under the RCP 8.5 scenario. It is important to note that this increase in variability can significantly affect the geomorphological and ecological dynamics of the river and thus the diversity of the river (López-Ballesteros et al., 2020). Accordingly, variability based on the 10th and 90th percentiles will also increase, although to a more limited extent than extreme variability.

Table 9. Quantification of the impact of climate change on the magnitude and variability.

Parameter	RCM model	Baseline (1976-2005)	RCP 4.5 (2040-2069)	RCP 4.5 (2070-2099)	RCP 8.5 (2040-2069)	RCP 8.5 (2070-2099)
Mean (hm ³)	IPSL-CM5A- LR	74.37	74.01	76.47	76.88	93.23
	MIROC	50.57	47.63	47.88	48.79	58.47
	NoerESM1-M	59.51	81.23	78.39	83.60	105.51
EV (hm ³)	IPSL-CM5A- LR	5.13	4.94	5.58	5.15	7.74
	MIROC	2.66	2.92	3.06	3.07	4.98
	NoerESM1-M	4.36	6.84	5.90	6.88	8.26
Q10% (m ³ /s)	IPSL-CM5A- LR	3.33	3.15	3.33	3.31	4.08
	MIROC	2.05	2.03	2.07	2.10	2.67
	NoerESM1-M	2.52	3.60	3.48	3.71	4.75
Q90% (m ³ /s)	IPSL-CM5A- LR	1.53	1.63	1.63	1.71	2.03
	MIROC	1.22	1.13	1.11	1.14	1.28
	NoerESM1-M	1.29	1.67	1.65	1.71	2.19

The seasonality in which maximum and minimum flows occur in a river is an aspect that is closely and synchronously linked to the life cycles of the species (Ngor et al., 2018). As can be seen in table 10, climate change can significantly affect these life cycles. A delay is observed in the MaxRF, with respect to the maximums that tend to occur in the month of May and which in the future will occur more frequently in June. An increase in the frequency of these MaxRFs is also observed in December. Regarding the MinRFs, all models coincide in concentrating these MinRFs during the months of September-November. There is a clear tendency to delay the occurrence of these minimum values from September to November.

Table 10. Quantification of the impact of climate change on the seasonality.

Parameter	RCM model	Emission scenario	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	
Max RF	IPSL-CM5A-LR	Baseline (1976-2005)	0.00	0.00	0.38	0.10	0.14	0.21	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.17	
		RCP 4.5 (2040-2069)	0.03	0.00	0.21	0.07	0.00	0.45	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.24
		RCP 4.5 (2070-2099)	0.00	0.00	0.38	0.03	0.00	0.24	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.34
		RCP 8.5 (2040-2069)	0.00	0.03	0.10	0.14	0.03	0.45	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.24
		RCP 8.5 (2070-2099)	0.03	0.03	0.14	0.00	0.00	0.45	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.34
	MIROC	Baseline (1976-2005)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.38	0.59	0.03	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
		RCP 4.5 (2040-2069)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.10	0.90	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
		RCP 4.5 (2070-2099)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.24	0.76	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
		RCP 8.5 (2040-2069)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.28	0.72	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
		RCP 8.5 (2070-2099)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.38	0.59	0.03	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	NoerESM1-M	Baseline (1976-2005)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.14	0.41	0.21	0.07	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.17
		RCP 4.5 (2040-2069)	0.07	0.00	0.00	0.03	0.28	0.14	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.48
		RCP 4.5 (2070-2099)	0.03	0.00	0.00	0.24	0.17	0.21	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.34
		RCP 8.5 (2040-2069)	0.03	0.00	0.00	0.10	0.21	0.10	0.07	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.48
		RCP 8.5 (2070-2099)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.07	0.07	0.21	0.03	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.62
Min RF	IPSL-CM5A-LR	Baseline (1976-2005)	0.03	0.14	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.03	0.28	0.21	0.31	0.00	
		RCP 4.5 (2040-2069)	0.07	0.10	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.03	0.10	0.14	0.55	0.00
		RCP 4.5 (2070-2099)	0.03	0.03	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.31	0.21	0.41	0.00
		RCP 8.5 (2040-2069)	0.03	0.10	0.00	0.00	0.03	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.03	0.31	0.07	0.41	0.00
		RCP 8.5 (2070-2099)	0.03	0.07	0.00	0.07	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.03	0.10	0.24	0.45	0.00
	MIROC	Baseline (1976-2005)	0.00	0.28	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.66	0.03	0.03	0.00
		RCP 4.5 (2040-2069)	0.00	0.28	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.24	0.24	0.24	0.00
		RCP 4.5 (2070-2099)	0.00	0.17	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.10	0.31	0.41	0.00
		RCP 8.5 (2040-2069)	0.07	0.17	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.21	0.28	0.28	0.00
		RCP 8.5 (2070-2099)	0.00	0.28	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.66	0.03	0.03	0.00
	NoerESM1-M	Baseline (1976-2005)	0.00	0.03	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.90	0.07	0.00	0.00
		RCP 4.5 (2040-2069)	0.00	0.07	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.69	0.10	0.14	0.00
		RCP 4.5 (2070-2099)	0.00	0.07	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.03	0.76	0.03	0.10	0.00
		RCP 8.5 (2040-2069)	0.00	0.03	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.07	0.66	0.10	0.14	0.00
		RCP 8.5 (2070-2099)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.17	0.28	0.21	0.34	0.00

5. Conclusions

This paper has evaluated the impact of projected climate change scenarios on renewable groundwater resources in the PRB. Three selected RCM models (IPSL-CM5A-LR, MIROC and NoerESM1-M) demonstrated a general increase in average annual temperature, ranging from +2°C, in the mid-term, to +4.5°C, in the long term. However, average annual precipitation increased between +3% and +20%, and even as high as +41% in the RCP 8.5 scenario. Although the increase in precipitation (P) will induce higher streamflow, the increase in temperature (T) is more relevant and could increase actual evapotranspiration (ET), reducing streamflow and aquifer recharge. Aquifer recharge better correlates with the evaporative (ET:P ratio) and non-evaporative (1-[ET:P] ratio) fractions of P rather than P or ET. The IPSL-CM5A-LR and MIROC models revealed a general decrease in aquifer recharge, although this trend was softened, or even reversed, in several long-term scenarios. Conversely, the NoerESM1-M model significantly increased aquifer recharge in the mid and long term, which is consistent with admission of more recharge events as the aquifer empties moderately in a context of lower water resources availability in the future. Furthermore, this final RCM model exhibited greater differences in seasonal aquifer recharge regarding the baseline scenario. The difference was as high as +23% during the wet season in the long term.

The satisfactory performance on the monthly scale was a prerequisite for considering the SWAT model suitable for long-term water resources evaluation. However, underestimations of streamflow peaks indicate additional uncertainty extending to streamflow and aquifer recharge predictions in the mid and long term regarding equivalent predictions in the baseline scenario. Similarly, weak performance on the daily scale could limit SWAT model application when predicting extraordinary flood events and rapid groundwater response, expected following soil degradation and higher rainfall intensities induced by global warming in the future.

Regarding the significance of renewable groundwater resources in the PRB, in particular, and the Andean highlands, in general, future research should aim to refine future predictions based on necessary groundwater monitoring to support specific groundwater modelling tools. For example, coupled SWAT-MODFLOW models have proven satisfactory solutions, provided piezometry can be monitored long-term and hydraulic parameters for aquifers and hydraulically connected aquitards can be surveyed accurately. Similarly, uncertainty in RCM results could be reduced by extending the comparison to more data-demanding climate change scenarios, which is currently unfeasible based on existing data.

Despite these unavoidable limitations, the model results are sufficiently confident to provide detailed insights into uncertainties regarding groundwater resources and improve the knowledge base required to enhance decision-making based on sustainability. Furthermore, the model results can help forecast hydrological stress trends and subsequent ecological risks in Andean alpine ecosystems. Although this paper focuses on the PRB, it aims to provide the foundation for studies in other data-scarce basins in the andosol-dominated Andean highlands, where global warming is already affecting traditional freshwater availability.

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